
FORECASTING DEMAND FOR MOSLEM FASHION PRODUCTS AT DG COMPANY IN SOUTH TANGERANG, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Online fashion business is very promising in this era of globalization because of its vast market and it is always needed at all times. But companies must be smart in managing this business because the demand is usually very volatile. DG company took part in enlivening this industry with specialization in production and sales of teenage muslimah (moslem women) clothing. This study aims to forecast the demand for abaya products in DG Company for January to December 2017. The benefit of this research is to provide a forecasting technique that can assist the company in performing production planning in order to achieve efficiency of production resources. The forecasting is based on 2016 sales data records. The forecasting methodology used is the trend method. There are three forecasting models that are assumed to be suitable for existing data trends, ie linear model, quadratic polynomial model, and cyclical model. After doing some calculation about forecast error and statistical test of the three forecasting models, finally it was found that linear forecasting model was the best model with SEE = 1,442575 and MSE = 1,997781. The linear forecasting results were then verified using the moving range chart and the results show that all forecasting data results were within the control limits. Thus the linear forecasting method was felt to be able to provide the best forecasting to determine the monthly production amount throughout 2017.

Keywords : demand forecasting, forecasting accuracy, fashion.

Introduction

Demand forecasting plays an important role in operations management as an input for planning activities. Bad forecasting effects are stock outs or high inventories, expired or inefficient resource utilization and will propagate the supply chain. Usually, high-performance firms will focus on strong demand forecast approaches. According to Beutel (2012), the challenge of forecasting demand varies widely among companies and industries.

Forecasting is a business activity that needs to be done by every company to get information and input for business decision making (Shahabuddin, 2009). This is due to the uncertainty and fluctuations in demand for a product. In addition, the competition in the world of fashion business is also increasingly tight, so every company must control its production in such a way by planning its proper production, in order to be able to meet consumer demands appropriately, and able to apply efficiency in production costs. According to Buffa (1996), forecasting is a very important and integrated keyword in a production plan, where the amount of production and use of other resources such as production materials, labor, production schedules and machinery must follow the forecasting that has been done. By forecasting the amount of demand for products or services in the coming period can be estimated so that efficiency can be achieved within the company. According to Gasperz (2004) past experience is needed to estimate production planning.

In a study conducted by Xiao (2007 and 2008) it is explained that sales forecasting is becoming more important because of the increasingly fierce competition and globalization. According to Eppen (1997), effective sales forecasting can help decision-making in calculating production costs, raw materials, and to determine the selling price. The result will be lower inventory levels, faster response, and more timely delivery. However, sales forecasting is usually a very complex problem because of the many factors influencing the internal and external environment, especially in the fashion industry (Kuo, 1999)

The fashion industry is a very attractive sector for sales forecasting. The long transformation process into fashion products in the market contrasts with the short life cycle, making forecasting of fashion products very challenging (Choi, 2014). The trend in the fashion model has caused consumer demands to be very volatile. Consumers want fashion designs to be always up to date. Consequently, historical sales are often not available because most items are temporary (Sen A, 2008). According to Thomassey, S. (2010) in Rodrigues (2013) in fashion business generally the products sold have short sales periods. The inventory management system must be aware of and ready for such market behavior. To reduce inventory levels, fashion retailers choose various policies such as providing quick response (Choi, 2006).

The development of moslem clothing business in Indonesia today is very rapid. Although Indonesia is a tropical country with quite hot weather, but the moslem fashion business that generally covers almost the entire

body is still growing rapidly. More and more young generations of moslems customize their clothing according to religious provisions. This is certainly a uniqueness in the world of fashion. However, the demand for moslem fashion is not always stable and quite volatile throughout the year. Therefore, forecasting of demand is necessary to achieve efficiency in the business.

This research was conducted at DG Company that produces moslem fashion located in South Tangerang. The type of fashion produced consist of dresses (abaya) for young moslem women. The problem is the uncertainty and the ups and downs in the demand for these fashion products. The company is keen to obtain information on how large the demand for this type of fashion is in 2017 in order to make a production that meets all requests and does not allow any surplus or stock shortage. Therefore, the purpose of this study are 1) to determine the correct demand forecasting model for 2017 and 2) to determine the size of the estimated demand for this fashion product for each month in 2017 as accurately as possible.

Materials and Methods

The Concept of Forecasting

Forecasting is very urgent in production planning. Forecasting can minimize risks that may occur due to uncertainty in demand and others. Forecasting uses the assumption that the characteristics of demand in the past will also apply in the coming periods. Forecasting activities involve various divisions within the company. A mistake in forecasting sales will affect the budget, cash flow, inventory, and others. To get accurate and efficient forecasting results, it is worth noting the following two important points (Makridakis, 1999): 1). Relevant data collection to be processed to obtain the correct forecasting results. 2) Selection of appropriate forecasting methods to be used to process the available data.

Data Patterns.

The analysis of time series data forecasting should be based on the data patterns. The patterns of demand data for a product can be determined by drawing a scatter diagram of the demand data over a given period. Scatter diagrams can illustrate the trendline of demands over a period. Four types of data patterns commonly found in forecasting are: Linear Patterns, Seasonal Patterns, Cyclic Patterns and Trend Patterns (Makridakis, 1999)

Measuring Forecasting Accuracy.

Forecasting is an approximation or prediction about something in the future. Forecasting is done using existing past data and using appropriate forecasting methods. Statistically, a forecast is accurate if it has a small forecast error. The measuring tools used to calculate forecasting accuracy include Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD), Mean Square of Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Of Error (MAPE), and Standard Error of Estimate (SEE).

Research Method

The research was conducted at DG Company located in South Tangerang, Indonesia. DG Company is engaged in the production of moslem clothing. The object of this research is to do forecasting for abaya dresses for the year 2017. The secondary data used is the quantity of sales (in units) of product in the past period. Weekly data is obtained from sales records along 2016. Referring to Maulidah (2014), the research method follows the following steps:

- Plot a trend line of data
- Estimate the data model based on trendline with some models that are expected to be suitable.
- Calculate forecasting error for each model
- Select 2 models with the smallest forecast error
- Do statistical test f to determine the best model of both selected models, where:

$$f = \frac{(SEE_{\text{mod } el-1})^2}{(SEE_{\text{mod } el-2})^2}$$

with the hypothesis:

H_0 : model-1 is better than model-2 if $f_{\text{test}} \leq f_{\text{table}}$

H_1 : model-1 is not better than model 2 if $f_{\text{test}} > f_{\text{table}}$

- Do forecasting verification using moving range chart,

$$\overline{MR} = \frac{\sum_{t=2}^{n-1} MR_t}{n-1},$$

where $MR_t = |e_t - e_{t-1}|$,

$$UCL = 2,66 \times \overline{MR}, \quad LCL = -2,66 \times \overline{MR}$$

Decision : If all points are within the constraint limit (UCL and LCL), then the model is assumed to be good

Result and Discussion

Figure 1. shows the weekly sales during 2016. The data has been taken from company records.

Figure 1. Graph of Total Sales Period 2016

The next step is to select the forecasting model. Based on the data pattern in the scatter diagram, some models that may be suitable for forecasting are Linear model, Quadratic model, and Cyclical model. Therefore it is necessary to investigate which model is most appropriate for forecasting

a. Forecasting Using Linear Model. The general form of forecasting by linear method is: $y = a + bx$,

where a and b are: $a = \frac{\sum Y \sum X^2 - \sum X \sum XY}{n \sum (X^2) - (\sum X)^2}$, $b = \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{n \sum (X^2) - (\sum X)^2}$

Using the above formula, we obtained $a = 204,0837$ and $b = -1,942927$, so the forecasting equation is:

$$Y = 204,0837 - 1,942927 X$$

The best method used for forecasting is the method with the smallest error rate. Here we use SEE and MSE to calculate the forecasting error rate of each method because it is more suitable with the data characteristics and problems solved. The SEE and MSE calculation gave a result as:

$$SEE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (Y - Y')^2}{n - f}} = 1,442575; \quad MSE = \frac{\sum (Y - Y')^2}{n} = 1,997781$$

b. Forecasting Using Quadratic Model. The general equation for forecasting using the quadratic method is

$y = a + bx + cx^2$. After doing some calculations, it was found the values of a, b, and c as follows:

$a = 155,85$; $b = 3,5979$, and $c = -0,1081$

So the forecasting equation is: $y = 155,85 + 3,5979X - 0,1081X^2$

The forecasting error is shown as:

$$SEE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (Y - Y')^2}{n - f}} = 69,07; \quad MSE = \frac{\sum (Y - Y')^2}{n} = 4,587$$

c. Forecasting Using Cyclical Model. The general equation of forecasting on cyclical methods is:

$$y = a + b \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x + c \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x$$

The formula used to get the cyclical model parameter was as follows:

$$\sum Y = na + b \sum \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x + c \sum \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x$$

$$7.835 = 52a \rightarrow a = 150,67$$

$$\sum Y \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x = a \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x + b \sum \sin^2 \frac{2\pi}{n} x + c \sum \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x$$

$$1.150 = 1.352 b \rightarrow b = 0,85$$

$$\sum Y \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x = a \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x + b \sum \cos^2 \frac{2\pi}{n} x + c \sum \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x$$

$$-958 = 26c \rightarrow c = -36,84$$

So the forecasting equation is:

$$Y = 150,67 + 0,85 \sin \frac{2\pi}{n} x - 36,84 \cos \frac{2\pi}{n} x$$

The cyclical forecasting errors are :

SEE = 1.122,19976 and MSE = 1.210.896

d. Selection of Forecasting Model and Statistical Testing. Based on the three forecasting forms outlined above, the comparison of forecasting errors is as follows;

Table 1- Forecasting Errors Comparison

Forecasting Model	SEE	MSE
Linear	1,44	2,00
Quadratic	69,07	4.587,29
Cyclical	1.122,20	1.210.896,44

From the above SEE and MSE values, the linear and quadratic methods are able to give the smallest error value. However, it is necessary to do statistical test using the f distribution first before choosing which of these two methods will be used to forecast production in the coming period.

For $\alpha=5\%$, Statistical test :

$$f = \frac{(SEE_{linear})^2}{(SEE_{Quadratic})^2} = 0,000302377 ; \text{ Table: } f_{0,05} (51,51) = 1,6$$

Test results: $f_{test} < f_{table}$, then H_0 is accepted.

So the linear method is better than the quadratic method.

e. Forecasting Verification. To determine whether the forecasting results are in the control limit, it is necessary to verify the data. The forecast verification of cyclical methods was performed using the moving range chart: $\overline{MR} = 1.391,69/51 = 27,28804178$, $UCL = 2,66 \times \overline{MR} = 72,59$; $LCL = -2,66 \times \overline{MR} = -72,59$; $1/3 UCL = 24,20$; $1/3 LCL = -24,20$; $2/3 UCL = 48,39$; $2/3 LCL = -48,39$
Based on the above results, the moving range chart is shown in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Moving Range Chart for Linear Model

From Figure 2, there is no data coming out of the control limits, so the linear forecasting equation is the best model to forecast demand for 2017.

Forecasting Result

Based on linear model, demand forecasts can be obtained for the year 2017 as follows:

Table 2- Forecasting Results for the year 2017

Month	Week	Demand Forecasting (unit)	Month	Week	Demand Forecasting (unit)
January (991)	I	202	July (595)	I	152
	II	200		II	150
	III	198		III	148
	IV	196		IV	146
	V	194		Augustus(700)	I
February (758)	I	192	II		142
	II	190	III		140
	III	189	IV		138
	IV	187	V		136
March (727)	I	185	September (525)	I	134
	II	183		II	132
	III	181		III	130
	IV	179		IV	128
April (696)	I	177	October (612)	I	126
	II	175		II	124
	III	173		III	122
	IV	171		IV	121
May(826)	I	169		V	119
	II	167	November (455)	I	117
	III	165		II	115
	IV	163		III	113
	V	161		IV	111
June (626)	I	159		December (424)	I
	II	157	II		107
	III	156	III		105
	IV	154	IV		103

Conclusion

1. The most suitable model used to forecast product demand in DG company is the linear model
2. The results of the demand forecast for abaya products, from January to December 2017 are 991, 758, 727, 696, 826, 626, 595, 700, 525, 612, 455, and 424 units respectively.

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